

ADHESION AND DEGRADATION OF WELL-DESIGNED TITANIUM-PEEK INTERFACES WITHIN TITANIUM-CF/PEEK LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Fibre Metal Laminates (FML) consisting of alternating stacked layers of polymer matrix composites (PMC) and metallic foils are considered for structures with high fracture toughness and good impact resistance in aeronautic applications [1]. They combine the advantages of PMC and metals and overcome their disadvantages simultaneously. In comparison to glass fiber reinforced aluminum (GLARE[®]), carbon fiber reinforced polymers combined with titanium foils exhibit higher strengths and stiffness. When using thermoplastics as matrix material for the PMC, further advantages arise such as formability and weldability as well as low environmental impact. The properties of thermoplastic FML composed of titanium and carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone (Ti-CF/PEEK laminates) are under investigation at DLR (German Aerospace Center).

Despite of the evident advantages, these new materials still require systematic improvements to resolve short-comings that limit their applications. Particularly, the degradation of adhesion between the polyetheretherketone (PEEK) matrix and titanium is an issue: humidity is a critical factor for the aging of Ti-CF/PEEK laminates. Good adhesion and moisture resistance of the metal-polymer interface require well-designed surface pre-treatments. Investigations showed that laser surface pre-treatments of titanium and its alloys create a micro-structured oxide layer and enhance the surface wettability. Thus, the laser induced surface pre-treatment leads to hydrothermally stable adhesion when bonded to chemically cured adhesives [2-5], such as thermosets. Comparative examination of physical, chemo-physical and chemical surface pre-treatments

evidenced that surface pre-treatments with a pulsed Nd:YAG laser (physical pre-treatment) offer both good adhesion and superior moisture resistance of the interface between titanium and physically curing thermoplastic PEEK interface [6]. Moreover, laser treatments offer production related and environmental advantages (automatable, no chemicals required).

Therefore, the objective of this investigation is to examine the interface between titanium and PEEK in order to determine the adhesion mechanism and also the reason for the greatly improved degradation resistance. Since the delamination of metal-polymer interfaces initiates and propagates by superposed mode I and mode II loading, the titanium-PEEK interface delamination behavior is characterized with mixed mode bending (MMB) experiments according to ASTM D6671 [7]. The mixed mode bending experiments, first suggested by Crews and Reeder [8], are conducted to obtain the load-displacement response and thoroughly analyze the interlaminar fracture mechanisms of the Ti-CF/PEEK laminates under various mixed mode ratios before and after hydrothermal aging.

2 Experimental procedure

2.1 Test specimen

The materials used in this investigation were titanium sheets (TiAl3V2.5, Grade 9) with a thickness of 1.6mm, unidirectional CFRP tapes consisting of AS4 carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone (60vol.% CF) with a thickness of 0.14mm manufactured by TenCate, pure polyetheretherketone foil with a thickness of 0.1mm, and polyimide foil with a thickness of 0.25mm. Before manufacturing the Ti-CF/PEEK laminates the titanium surface was pre-treated by a pulsed Nd:YAG laser (1064 nm) in am-

bient air (CleanLaser system). Thereby, the near-surface titanium is melted, partly ablated, and subsequently quenched.

The manufactured Ti-CF/PEEK laminates consists of one inner unidirectional CFRP tape and two outer titanium sheets. Between the inner CFRP tape and the outer titanium sheets an additional PEEK foil is placed (elastic layer). To obtain a well-defined delamination process according to ASTM D6671 [7], a 50mm width polyimide film (release film) is placed between the pure PEEK foil and the titanium sheet as a delamination starter. The layers are stacked together as described previously (Fig. 1), heated up to 400°C well above the melting temperature of PEEK, consolidated and subsequently cooled down under pressure (hot press molding). During cooling process the PEEK solidifies and adheres to titanium. Laminates with dimensions of about 150mm x 150 mm were produced and cut by water jet to final specimen size with a length of 150mm and a width of 25mm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Stacking sequence of the MMB specimen.

Fig. 2. Dimensions of prepared MMB specimen.

2.2 Mixed mode bending experiments

Typically, delamination failures in adhesively bonded joints initiate and propagate under the combined influence of normal and shear stresses. Crews and Reeder [8] accomplished delamination testing of composite materials with combined tensile normal stress (mode I) and sliding shear stress (mode II) in their study. The MMB loading was represented by a superposition of simple mode I and mode II loadings (Fig. 3), conducted with a single load P. The loading

is then expressed in terms of the applied load P, the loading lever length c, and the half clamping length L (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Loading description of MMB experiment.

Fig. 4. MMB test apparatus (schematic).

The loading position defined by c determines the mixed mode ratio. Pure mode II loading occurs when the applied load is directly above the beam mid-span (c = 0). The fraction of mode II decreases with increasing values of the loading position c (c > 0). Pure mode I loading can be achieved by removing the beam when pulling apart at the hinge. The corresponding loading lever lengths c for the mixed mode ratios are calculated according to P. P. Camanho and C. G. Davila [9]. The mixed mode ratios investigated in this study are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Lever length for the mixed mode ratios

Mode I	Mode II	Loading position c
100%	0%	without loading lever
70%	30%	90.0 mm
50%	50%	56.8 mm
20%	80%	36.5 mm
0%	100%	0 mm

A servo hydraulic testing machine equipped with 100kN load cells is used for testing. The MMB test apparatus as described above (Fig. 4) is placed into the servo hydraulic testing machine. The cross-head displacement rate was 0.5 mm/min for all the specimens. The load-displacement response was recorded

by using a digital data acquisition system. The specimen is recorded by a digital camera during the MMB test procedure in order to investigate the delamination growth. At least two to four specimens were tested for each mixed mode ratio before and after hydrothermal aging. Hydrothermal aging is accomplished by exposure to hot water (80°C) for 28 days.

Typically, the strain energy release rate G is used for composite materials. It is defined as the derivative of the potential energy U , with respect to the crack extension area A . The crack will propagate when the strain energy release rate reaches a certain value G_C . The equation for mode I and mode II strain energy release rates (G_I and G_{II}) originate from beam theory equations later corrected by energy associated with shear deformation and the rotation of arms at the delamination tip [7].

As it is seen from Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), G_I and G_{II} are calculated by the applied load P , the loading lever length c , the half clamping length L , the propagating crack length a , the crack tip correction factor χ , and the mechanical properties and geometrical dimensions of the specimen (b : specimen width, E_{1f} : flexural stiffness in fiber direction, h : half specimen thickness) [7-8]. For the calculation of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} the critical value of the applied load is chosen as the load corresponding to the 1st visible nonlinearity in load–displacement curve (NL) [7]. The critical delamination length is the propagation crack length marked through the experiment.

$$G_I = \frac{3P^2(3c-L)^2}{4b^2h^3L^2E_{1f}}(a - \chi h)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2(c+L)^2}{16b^2h^3L^2E_{1f}}(a + 0,42\chi h)^2 \quad (2)$$

2.3 Analytical procedure

The examination of the adhesion and degradation mechanism at the interface between titanium and PEEK involves the analysis of the titanium surface before and after laser pre-treatment, the titanium-PEEK interface within the titanium-CF/PEEK laminate after manufacturing (thermal aging during consolidation at 400°C), and after hydrothermal aging by exposure to hot deionized water (80°C).

The type and location of failure are determined from the fracture surface of the MMB specimens and are compared for two sample sets, one with and another without hydrothermal aging. The used analytical methods are scanning electron microscopy (SEM),

transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Mixed mode bending experiment

The strain energy release rate is often an efficient measure of a material’s resistance to delamination extension. The mixed mode failure response of the Ti-CF/PEEK laminate is described by plotting the total critical fracture toughness G_C vs. different mixed mode ratio G_I/G_T (Figs. 5 and 6).

Fig. 5. Critical energy release rate G_C as a function of mixed mode ratio for non-aged specimen.

Fig. 6. Critical energy release rate G_C as a function of mixed mode ratio for aged specimen.

The mixed mode ratios equal to the mode II fraction. G_T stands for total fracture toughness (Eq. (3)).

$$G_T = G_I + G_{II} \quad (3)$$

The energy release rate progression of non-aged and aged specimen of the tested hybrid laminates is not in accordance with composite materials containing no metal layers. The energy release rate energy of Ti-CF/PEEK laminates exhibit a minimum at a mode mixed ratio of around 40%. The energy re-

lease rate increases with increasing mode I fraction and also with increasing mode II fraction. The equation to calculate the degradation caused by hydrothermal aging is given in Eq. (4).

$$\text{Degradation} = \frac{G_{C,unaged} - G_{C,aged}}{G_{C,unaged}} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

The degradation is summed up on table 2. The degradation of $G_{II}/G_T < 50\%$ is about 77% (without considering the G_{II}/G_T of 30%). The degradation of $G_{II}/G_T > 50\%$ is about 87%. The low degradation of G_{II}/G_T of 30% doesn't indicate a high humidity resistance but rather the low values already shown before aging. Both, aged and non-aged specimen exhibit higher values of the energy release rate when tested with a pure mode II loading.

Table 2: Degradation caused by hydrothermal aging

Mode mixed ratio G_{II}/G_T	Degradation
0%	76,97%
30%	32,35%
50%	77,40%
80%	88,01%
100%	85,31%

3.2 Analytical procedure

The used titanium sheets are contaminated at their surface by the rolling process. Lubricants used during rolling penetrate into the near-surface layers by tribochemical processes. The laser pre-treatment removes these surface and sub-surface contaminations in near-surface and at the surface. Since the laser pre-treatment cleans the surface no further cleaning steps were necessary. The laser treatment also leads to a highly reproducible surface structuring at different length scales with depressions and welding beads being formed (Fig. 7). The depressions are evenly arranged and vary little in size, i.e. length, width, and depth. The surface doesn't exhibit any sharp edges, neither at the depressions nor at their rims.

Fig. 7. SEM overview image of laser pre-treated titanium surface. The homogeneous distribution of the depressions is clearly visible.

Fig. 8. TEM image of a cross-section of the structured oxide layer of laser pre-treated titanium surface.

The oxide columns are about 0.5 to 1 μm in length and 0.1 to 0.2 μm in diameter. Measurements by the analytical TEM and XPS show that the core of the oxide columns consists of titanium monoxide TiO while they are covered with a thin titanium dioxide TiO_2 layer. The layer beneath the structured surface is affected by the laser induced heat introduction resulting in martensitic titanium with a thickness of about 1 to 2 μm . A model of the titanium surface layers is shown in Fig. 9.

The changes of the macro- and micro-structured surface topography that occurs during the manufacturing of the Ti-CF/PEEK laminates at 400°C (thermal aging) are negligible. During the consolidation phase the liquid PEEK diffuses into the capillary gaps of the oxide columns providing micro mechanical adhesion and also into the undercuts between the depressions and crater rims providing macro mechanical adhesion.

Fig. 9. Model of titanium surface layers caused by laser pre-treatment.

2.4 Fracture analysis

Both, the adhesion and the failure occur at the macro and micro structure level. Fig. 10 (a) shows the PEEK in the capillary gaps of the oxide columnar structure, which causes the micro mechanical adhesion. In the case of a mechanical loading, the PEEK molecules orientate and act as a structural reinforcement. The titanium fracture surface observed with SEM corroborates the orientated PEEK molecule at the titanium-PEEK interface (Fig. 11). Some constricted PEEK remained on the titanium fracture (Figs. 12a and 12b) and together with the constricted PEEK observed on the PEEK surface (Fig. 12c) indicates that a ductile failure mechanism was effective here.

Fig. 10. Adhesion and failure mechanism of the columnar oxide layer.

However, the failure not only occurred within the PEEK in the near-surface, but also in and beneath the columnar oxide layer (Fig. 10 (b)). The PEEK

fracture surface contains remaining oxide columns (Fig. 13). That indicates that the failure occurred in and beneath the columnar oxide structure.

Fig. 11. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 100\%$, aged) with “PEEK molecule reinforced” titanium-PEEK interface.

Fig. 12a. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 0\%$, non-aged) with remaining PEEK.

Fig. 12b. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 50\%$, non-aged) with remaining PEEK.

Fig. 12c. SEM image of PEEK fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 30\%$, non-aged) that indicates ductile failure at the titanium-PEEK interface.

Fig. 13. SEM image of PEEK fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 50\%$, aged) with remaining columnar oxide layer.

The mechanism of micro mechanical adhesion appears dominantly at high mode I fraction and decreases with increasing mode II fraction. The micro mechanical adhesion also decreases by the hydrothermal aging.

Additionally, the macro structured surface can also create mechanical adhesion. The macro mechanical adhesion is marked by PEEK which is left in the undercuts between the depression and the crater rim. The titanium fracture surface tested at high mode II load fraction shows a rather large amount of residual PEEK within the undercuts (Fig. 14). The constricted PEEK remaining in the undercuts of the titanium fracture surface again indicates ductile failure mechanism.

Fig. 14. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 80\%$, non-aged) with remaining PEEK within undercuts.

The mechanism of macro mechanical adhesion appears dominantly at high mode II fraction and decreases with increasing mode I fraction. Non-aged specimens with pure mode I loading exhibits nearly no macro mechanical adhesion. The micro mechanical adhesion also weakens dramatically due to the influence of hydrothermal exposure.

Instead of micro mechanical adhesion as observed on the non-aged samples, the aged specimen exhibit partly disrupted weld spatter (Fig. 15a). A closer look to the disrupted weld spatter depicts the some pores beneath the weld spatter (Fig. 15b). They are likely caused by shrinkage during the quick cooling period on air after the heating phase in the laser pre-treatment and significantly influence the moisture resistance of the titanium-PEEK interface.

Fig. 15a. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 80\%$, aged) with removed macro structure by hydrothermal aging.

Fig.15b. SEM image of titanium fracture surface ($G_{II}/G_T = 80\%$, non-aged) with pores beneath the weld spatter.

2.5 Discussion

Both, aged and non-aged specimens exhibit higher energy release rates when tested at pure mode II loading. Aged and non-aged specimens tested at pure mode I loading adheres micro mechanically. Specimen with pure mode I loading exhibits nearly no macro mechanical adhesion and also nearly no disrupted weld spatter. Non-aged specimens tested at pure mode II loading adheres micro mechanically (reduced) and macro mechanically simultaneously. The superposed mechanical adhesion of non-aged specimens leads to higher energy release rates compared to pure mode I loading. Aged specimens tested at pure mode II loading adhere micro mechanically and fail additionally due to partly disrupted weld spatter. The superposed micro mechanical adhesion and required energy for disruption of partly weld spatter leads to higher energy release rates.

The degradation of specimens tested at low mixed mode ratios ($G_{II}/G_T < 50\%$) caused by hydrothermal aging is lower than the degradation of the specimens tested at high mixed mode ratios ($G_{II}/G_T > 50\%$). The micro mechanical adhesion appears dominantly at high mode I fraction and decreases with increasing mode II fraction. The mechanism of macro mechanical adhesion appears dominantly at high mode II fraction and decreases with increasing mode I fraction. Specimens with pure mode I loading exhibits nearly no macro mechanical adhesion. The results obtained support the correlation between surface morphology and adhesive bond durability, as already described by Venables [10] and also by Brown and Pilla [11] who established that by micro structured surfaces leads to enhanced bond durability.

Some pores are detected beneath the weld spatter, which are most probably caused by shrinkage during the quenched cooling after the laser cleaning procedure and affect the moisture resistance of the interface. The micro mechanical adhesion degrades most probably due to humidity that diffuses from the edges of the laminate into titanium-PEEK interface and migrates to the center. In order to confirm and further understand the exact bonding and degradation mechanisms further investigations will be necessary.

4 Summary

In this investigation the adhesion and degradation mechanism at well-designed titanium-PEEK interfaces within Ti-CF/PEEK laminates are examined by mixed mode bending, scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy, and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy experiments.

Surface laser pre-treatments were employed to produce macro and micro structured surfaces. The laser induced micro structured surface consists of an columnar oxide layer. The oxide columns have a length of about 0.5 to 1 μm and a diameter of about 0.1 to 0.2 μm . The core of the columns consists of titanium monoxide TiO which is covered by a thin titanium dioxide TiO_2 layer. The macro mechanical adhesion causes high energy release rates when loaded in mode II loading but also insufficient humidity resistance when exposed to hydrothermal environments. The micro mechanical adhesion also causes high energy release rates not only when loaded in mode I loading but also when loaded in mode II loading. In comparison to macro mechanical adhesion the micro mechanical exhibits good humidity resistance when exposed to hydrothermal environments.

Testing the specimen with mode II loading, superposed effects lead to high energy release rates whereas testing with mode I loading suggests that it is single effects that lead to lower energy release rates.

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References

- [1] T. Sinmazçelik, E. Avcu, M. Bora, and O. Çoban “A review: Fibre metal laminates, background, bonding types and applied test methods”. *Materials & Design* Vol. 32, No. 7, pp 3671-3685, 2011
- [2] E. Sancaktar and E. Zhang “Laser ablation of aluminium and titanium surfaces for improved adhesion”. *Reliability stress analysis and failure prevention aspects of composite and active materials* Vol.79, 1994
- [3] P. Molitor and P. Young “Adhesives bonding of a titanium alloy to a glass fibre reinforced composite material”. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* Vol. 22, No. 2, pp 101-107, 2002
- [4] E. G. Baburaj, D. Starikov, J. Evans, G. A. Shafeev and A. Bensaoula “Enhancement of adhesive joint strength by laser surface modification”. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* Vol. 27, No. 4, pp 268-276, 2007
- [5] S. Zimmermann, U. Specht, L. Spieß, H. Romanus, S. Krischok, M. Himmerlich and J. Ihde “Improved adhesion at titanium surfaces via laser-induced surface oxidation and roughening”. *Materials Science and Engineering: A* Vol. 558, No. 0, pp 755-760, 2012
- [6] K. Schulze, J. Hausmann and B. Wielage “The Stability of Different Titanium-PEEK Interfaces against Water”. *Procedia Materials Science* Vol. 2, No.0, pp 92-102, 2013
- [7] ASTM D6671/D6671M – 06 Standard Test Method for Mixed Mode I-Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites, 2006
- [8] J. H. Crews and J. R. Reeder “A mixed-mode bending apparatus for delamination testing”. Citeseer, 1988
- [9] P. P. Camanho and C. G. Davila “Mixed-Mode Decohesion Finite Elements for the Simulation of Delamination in Composite Materials”. NASA/TM-2002-211737, 2002
- [10] J. D. Venables “Adhesion and durability of metal-polymer bonds”. *Journal of Materials Science* Vol. 19, pp 2431-2453, 1984
- [11] S. R. Brown and G. J. Pilla “Titanium Surface Treatments for Adhesive Bonding”. Technical Report No. NADC-82032-60, 1982